

THE ROLE OF FOLK ORAL CREATION IN EDUCATION OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article, it is considered that the role of folklore in the education of elementary school students is incomparable, to educate students in the spirit of nationalism, hard work, and patriotism, and at the same time to expand their worldview.

Key words: elementary school, nationality, patriotism, folklore, epic, fairy tale, riddle, hard work, friendship, love, upbringing, education, well-rounded personality, manners.

"Education and upbringing are like two wings of a bird. Just as a bird cannot fly with one wing, education and upbringing cannot be separated from each other," says our first president I. Karimov. It is known that today in our country great attention is paid to education. Folk art plays an important role in raising a child from a young age to be educated, well-educated, high-level, world-view.

President Sh. Mirziyoyev attached great importance to the education of the future young generation: "We will mobilize all the strength and capabilities of our state and society so that our young people can become independent thinkers, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, become people who are not inferior to their peers in any field in the world, and be happy." - they say. The subject of education was introduced in general secondary educational institutions on the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from the 2020-2021 academic year. In primary education textbooks, folklore plays a special role in educating a well-rounded person. The presentation of riddles from folklore in primary education textbooks encourages the child to think, search, and act quickly.

In addition, the student learns teamwork and cooperation in the process of finding the answer to the given riddle.

One of the richest and most colorful genres of folk poetry is a fairy tale. In many fairy tales created by the people, the unique life of children has not been left out. There are even many special fairy tales created for children of different ages. One of the important features of a fairy tale is that it is always closely connected with people's life, history, spiritual world, worldview, traditions, and becomes a moral and spiritual companion for people. They are always victorious in the fight against hostile forces. In folk tales, the worldview, moral norms and other socially important issues of its creators are also fairly discussed. As the tales are simple and understandable, they reach every reader quickly. The main idea of fairy tales is goodness, and through the characters in it, students learn to distinguish between the concepts of goodness and evil, and learn that goodness triumphs over all evil.

Dostanchik is an epic tradition in folk poetic creation. At first, songs were created to be sung without a musical instrument. Later epics were sung by Bakhshis. We can cite "Alpomish", "Ravshan", "Kuntug'mish" epics from Uzbek epics. These epics glorify feelings such as patriotism, hard work, true friendship, and respect for parents. The epics reflect the nationality, traditions and customs of the Uzbek people. It is these concepts that are very important in raising elementary school students to become well-rounded people.

In conclusion, I would like to say that it is appropriate to use examples of folk art in the education of elementary school students as mature and well-rounded individuals in the future. It is in this way that we, pedagogues, can eliminate the shortcomings of students' speech, educate well-rounded, educated people who can freely express their opinions and meet the demands of today.

References:

1. Sh. M. Mirziyoyev "Ta'lim sohasidagi muammolar, ularni hal etish va ta'lim sifatini oshirishga bag'ishlangan videoselektor mavzusida," 30.10.2020.

2. Norqobilova, R. D. (2023). USE of diagnostic tests in foreign schools. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal, 2(1), 359-364.

3. Mohinur Abdisamatova, Rayxona Norqobilova. INNOVATSION YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TARBIYA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISH. Том 1 № 1 (2023): ZAMONAVIY BOSHLANG‘ICH TA‘LIM: INNOVATSIYALAR, MUAMMOLAR VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI mavzusida Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari to‘plami.

4. Norqobilova Rayxona Davlatovna. Functions and Principles of Pedagogical Diagnostics. Vol. 2 No. 1 (2023): Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal.

5. Норқобилова, Р. (2023). Boshlang ‘ich sinf o ‘quvchilarining ona tilidan iqtidorini diagnostika qilish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish. *Общество и инновации*, 4(1/S), 36-41.

6. Abdullayeva, S. A., & Norqobilova, R. D. (2023). BOSHLANG ‘ICH SINFI O ‘QUVCHILARINING BILIM O‘ZLASHTIRISHLARINI DIAGNOSTIKA QILISH. *Interpretation and researches*, 1(1).

7. R.Norqobilova, M.To'rayeva Importance of talent in child development. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, VOLUME 3, ISSUE 7, July. 2022 57-61.

8. Ismoilova M., Norqobilova R. MATEMATIKA O‘QITISHDA INTERFAOL PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH //Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1.

9. Ashurova S., Norqobilova R. BOSHLANG‘ICH TA‘LIMDA OLIB BORILAYOTGAN ZAMONAVIY ISLOHOTLAR //Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1.

10. Ergasheva, M., & Norqobilova, R. (2023). BOSHLANG ‘ICH SINFI O‘QUVCHILARI DUNYOQARASHINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA KITOBXONLIKNING AHAMIYATI. *Interpretation and researches*, 2(1).

11. Mamatmurotova M., Norqobilova R. PAST O ‘ZLASHTIRUVCHI O‘QUVCHILAR BILAN ISHLASH METODIKASI//Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1.

12. Keldiyorova, M., & Norqobilova, R. (2023). BOSHLANG ‘ICH TA’LIMDA PEDAGOGIK-PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNING YECHIMLARI. *Interpretation and researches*, 2(1).

13. Ziyodullayeva, Z., & Norqobilova, R. (2023). BOSHLANG ‘ICH SINFLARDA “ONA TILI VA O‘QISH SAVODXONLIGI” DARSLARINI YANGICHA YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TASHKIL ETISH. *Interpretation and researches*, 1(1).

14. Norqobilova R. D. COMPONENT PARTS AND TASKS OF PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTICS //Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 6. – C. 76-83.

15. Kizi Z. S. K., Davlatovna N. R., Kizi T. B. M. high spiritual generation-third renaissance builders //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 5. – C. 167-169.

15. Норкабилова Р. ХОРИЙИ ФАНЛАДАН БОЛАЛАРНИНГ МАКТАБГА ТАЙЙОРГАРЛИГИНИНГ ДИАГНОСТИКАСИ //Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 11.

16. Normurodova H., Norgabilova R. VALUE OF MATHEMATICS IN PRIMARY GRADES //Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1.

17. Qahhorova M., Norqobilova R. BOSHLANG‘ICH SINF O‘QITUVCHILARINI TO‘G‘RI O‘QISHGA O‘RGATISH USULLARI //Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1.

18. Qobilova M., Norqobilova R. GLOBALLASHUV DAVRIDA MARKAZIY OSIYONING O‘TMISHI, BUGUNI VA ISTIQBOLINI O‘RGANISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI //Interpretation and

researches. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1.

19. Davlatovna, N. R. (2023). Functions and Principles of Pedagogical Diagnostics. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(1), 413-416.

20. Норкобилова, Р. (2022). О‘quvchilarning ona tili bo‘yicha iqtidorini aniqlash va rivojlantirishning o‘ziga xosligi. *Современные тенденции инновационного развития науки и образования в глобальном мире*, 1(3), 379-384.

21. Abdisamatova, M., & Norqobilova, R. (2023). INNOVATSION YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TARBIYA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISH. *Interpretation and researches*, 1(1).

22. Норкобилова, Р. 2023. Совершенствование механизмов диагностики владения родным языком учащихся начальных классов. *Общество и инновации*. 4, 1/S (янв. 2023), 36–41. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol4-iss1-pp36-41>.